

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ERUPTIVE AND POST ANOMALIES IN CHILDREN FROM DIVERSE BACKGROUNDS

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Abstract

Tooth eruption is defined as a movement of a tooth from its intraosseous site to its functional position of occlusion. The process consists of three stages: (a) pre-eruptive tooth movement, (b) eruptive tooth movement, and (c) posteruptive tooth movement.

Developmental dental anomalies can manifest as shape, form, number, and structural anomalies in the dentition, depending on the abnormal conditions and interactions in the embryological development process. Although the etiology of developmental dental anomalies, as in MIH, remains largely uncertain, many studies have been conducted to evaluate genetic and environmental factors in the origin of these anomalies. Consistent with the multilayered nature of the process, clinical outcome correlates with evidence of tissue changes and molecular genetic-epigenetic-environmental interactions.

The search strategy and selection process included relevant PICO terms, prospectively defined, following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guidelines. The following bibliographic databases were searched, and Mesh terms and Emtree were used: PubMed and Excerpta Medica Database (EMBASE).

247 records were retrieved for eligibility screening. Following a thorough process of filtering, we proceeded with the removal of duplicates, after which we settled on 131 records for the final stage. Screening of titles and abstracts excluded 119 records, reasoning whether said records were relevant or not to the aim of the review. We gathered 12 full texts of articles (two articles for qualitative synthesis and ten articles for quantitative synthesis). The included studies originated from diverse countries, with different views when talking about treatment and prophylactic protocols.

The main review objectives were to assess the international knowledge about the prevalence of eruptive anomalies in general population, mainly focusing on the group most recently affected by said affliction (the group of patients aged 8-18).

A better protocol must be elaborated in order to keep track of every pedodontic patient, the multitude of studies assessed showed increased difficulty in treating certain eruptive anomalies. Instating certain education programs for parents and future parents in order to communicate this international health concern is the way to improve the overall health of future generations.

Keywords: eruptive anomalies, occlusion, dental transposition, hypomineralization, fusion.

Introduction

Tooth eruption is defined as a movement of a tooth from its intraosseous site to its functional position of occlusion. The process consists of three stages: (a) pre-eruptive tooth movement, (b) eruptive tooth movement, and (c) posteruptive tooth movement. It has been generally accepted that this process depends on the equilibrium between the spaces in the path of eruption created by the dental follicle and the eruption pressure from apical tooth root formation. Dental follicle (DF) is a loose sac-like connective tissue surrounding the developing tooth. It comprises heterogeneous cell populations with two distinct roles during tooth eruption: activating and recruiting osteoclasts, and including mesenchymal progenitor cells that differentiate into

periodontal ligament cells, osteoblasts that form alveolar cryptal bone, and cementoblasts of the acellular cementum [1-8].

In the eruptive stage of tooth eruption, the crucial genes involve colony-stimulating factor-one (CSF-1), receptor activator of nuclear factor- κ B ligand (RANKL) and osteoprotegerin (OPG), which are abundantly expressed by dental follicle mesenchymal cells. These factors play important roles in the recruitment of cells in the monocyte-macrophage lineage and osteoclastogenesis. Therefore, in this stage, DF facilitates tooth eruption by activating osteoclasts and subsequently clearing the eruption pathway for unerupted teeth. However, in the later phase of eruptive stage, the formation of tooth root and periodontium plays important roles in tooth eruption. Parathyroid hormone-

related protein (PTHrP) and parathyroid hormone/PTHrP receptor (PPR) autocrine signaling are essential for regulating tooth eruption and tooth formation at this stage. PTHrP and PPR are highly expressed in a population of DF cells. Thus, dental follicle cells play critical dual roles throughout the process of tooth eruption [1,2].

The term of 'dental transposition' describes the change in position of a tooth with a neighboring tooth (only the crowns, only the roots or both) or the formation or eruption of a tooth in an ectopic distant position, after intraosseous migration, taking the place of a non-adjacent tooth. Other authors describe it as the change of the dental formula. Transpositions occur more frequently in the maxilla than in the mandible and also, they are usually unilateral, not bilateral. Transpositions can be complete, when both crowns and roots of the transposed teeth are switched, or incomplete, when the crowns are in transposed position, but the apices are still in their normal position, or when the crowns are on their regular position, but the roots are switched [1-3].

Molar incisor hypomineralization (MIH), a type of developmental and qualitative enamel defect that affects at least one permanent first molar and, depending on its severity, also affects the permanent incisors, was first described two decades ago. The global prevalence of MIH was reported to be 14.2%. An average of 878 million people suffer from MIH, with more than 17.5 million new cases each year. MIH, which is the most common developmental enamel defect from an epidemiological standpoint, affects nearly one out of every seven children, therefore, considering its global prevalence, it is important for public oral and dental health.

Developmental dental anomalies can manifest as shape, form, number, and structural anomalies in the dentition, depending on the abnormal conditions and interactions in the embryological development process. Although the etiology of developmental dental anomalies, as in MIH, remains largely uncertain, many studies have been conducted to evaluate genetic and environmental factors in the origin of these anomalies. Consistent with the multilayered nature of the process, clinical outcome correlates with evidence of tissue changes and molecular genetic-epigenetic-environmental interactions [4-6].

Defects can occur when one or more components of teeth or dento-skeletal development are compromised during amelogenesis. In addition, environmental effects, which are accepted as an essential factor in the etiology of both MIH and developmental dental anomalies, should not be ignored. Several gene families and mutations may play a role in the etiology of both MIH and developmental dental anomalies. Therefore, it was possible for various developmental dental anomalies to be observed in MIH and to affect dental development.

The etiology of the fusion of teeth is not completely known; however, it is believed that it involves physical force or pressure from the follicles of adjacent teeth, hereditary conditions, and racial determinants. The clinical appearance of the fusion depends on the developmental stage of the associated tooth buds. If

contact between 2 dental buds occurs before the calcification phase, full fusion occurs, presenting clinically as a single large crown [6-8].

If the fusion takes place in the advanced stage of morph-differentiation, it may be limited to the roots, meaning the fused teeth might have separate pulp chambers and root canals. Primary fused teeth (PFT) usually occur unilaterally and are more common in primary than in permanent dentition. They nearly always occur in the anterior region, and most often involve the mandibular lateral incisors and canines; occurrence in the posterior region is rare. Disturbance in tooth eruption is mostly caused by local factors and less frequently found in conjunction with systemic disease or syndrome. Primary failure of eruption (PFE) is a rare autosomal dominant non-syndromic disorder with a prevalence of 0.06% [5-9, 11].

Children are especially vulnerable to dental trauma, especially in the first two years of life, when they are starting to walk and socialize. The prevalence of trauma ranges from 4% to 33%. Epidemiological data show that approximately 30% of children aged <7 years have trauma in ≥ 1 primary incisor, and about 40% of children go to the dentist for the first time due to dental trauma. Due to the close relationship between the apex of primary teeth and the bud of permanent teeth, any lesion to the primary dentition may influence the eruption of the permanent teeth. The severity of sequelae depends on the patient's age, the degree of root reabsorption, the type and extent of the trauma, and the degree of development of the permanent successor at the time of trauma. Intrusion and avulsion of primary teeth are considered the types of traumas that produce the greatest number of alterations in the development of permanent teeth, according to various studies.

The main consequences of primary tooth trauma in the development of the permanent teeth are enamel discoloration, enamel hypoplasia, coronal dilaceration, root dilaceration, odontoma-like malformations, and alterations in eruption. Constant followup, with complementary tests, such as radiographs, and appropriate clinical interventions, can minimize or even prevent damage to the successor tooth [8-11].

The ectopic eruption of the first permanent molars represents a local eruption anomaly that causes the first permanent molars to remain blocked under the distal surface of the second deciduous molar, leading to its inability to erupt up to the level of the occlusal plane and to the pathological resorption of the second deciduous molar's roots. The etiology of the ectopic eruption of first permanent molars is multifactorial, including local, genetic and inherited factors, and its prevalence is different in various populations worldwide. The early diagnosis of ectopic eruption is necessary in order to prevent the development of other malocclusions and can be conducted with the help of routine panoramic radiographs. The radiographic sign that indicates a possible ectopic eruption of the first permanent molars is the superior and mesial position of the first permanent molars. Ectopic eruption can be classified into reversible and irreversible, the reversible form being the most common.

The treatment options for this anomaly depend on the patient's age, the status of the second deciduous molar, the presence of the second premolar, and the severity of the ectopy, and include interproximal wedging and distal tipping of the first permanent molar. The main goal of the early treatment of this pathology is to distance the ectopically erupting tooth from the deciduous tooth, to allow the normal eruption of the permanent tooth and to retain the deciduous molar on the dental arch until the physiological age of replacement [10-12].

Methods

The search strategy and selection process included relevant PICO terms, prospectively defined, following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guidelines. The following bibliographic databases were searched, and Mesh terms and Emtree were used: PubMed and Excerpta Medica Database (EMBASE).

The title, abstract and full text of each study were screened and accurately assessed. During the first phase screening of titles and abstracts, irrelevant records were basically categorized as intervention, opinion, reviews, participants, outcomes, not English language. The second-phase screening completely assessed the full article text of articles to verify the level of consistency that the studies had with the eligibility criteria. In addition, data extraction was gathered by formulating two tables using Windows Excel 2013.

Meanwhile, data that were extracted from the included criteria studies the risk of bias in studies that were detected simultaneously. For meta-analysis, we included 12 studies covering most dental anomalies found in the target group (patients aged between 8 and 18).

Results

247 records were retrieved for eligibility screening. Following a thorough process of filtering, we proceeded with the removal of duplicates, after which we settled on 131 records for the final stage. Screening of titles and abstracts excluded 119 records, reasoning whether said records were relevant or not to the aim of the review. We gathered 12 full texts of articles (two articles for qualitative synthesis and ten articles for quantitative synthesis). The included studies originated from diverse countries, with different views when talking about treatment and prophylactic protocols.

In the studies supervised by two pediatric dentists, resulted in the evaluation of panoramic radiographs from 429 children aged 8–14 years with molar incisor hypomineralization and 437 children without molar incisor hypomineralization in terms of developmental dental anomalies. Twelve different developmental dental anomalies were categorized into four types: size (microdontia, macrodontia); position (ectopic eruption of maxillary permanent first molars, infraocclusion of primary molars); shape (fusion, gemination, dilaceration, taurodontism, peg-shaped maxillary lateral incisors); and number (hypodontia, oligodontia, hyperdontia) anomalies.

No significant difference was observed in the frequencies of developmental dental anomalies between the study and control groups in total, females, and males ($p > 0.05$). A statistically significant difference was found between the distribution of developmental size, position, shape, and number anomalies between the study and control groups ($p = 0.024$). The most common anomaly in both groups was hypodontia (6.3% and 5.9%, respectively). There was a significant difference between the study and control groups in terms of subtypes of shape anomaly in all children and females ($p = 0.045$ and $p = 0.05$, respectively).

A total of 50 PFT were detected in the 40 patients. The mean age of patients was 6.7 ± 0.3 years (range 3–10 years). The most common PFT were the mandibular lateral incisors and canines (34, 68%). The most prevalent type of PFT was type III (20, 40%). Of the 40 patients with PFT, 34 (85%) also exhibited other dental anomalies such as tooth aplasia, peg-shaped incisors, talon cusps, ectopic eruption, and delayed eruption in both related and unrelated areas. The most common complications of PFT were fusion-related tooth aplasia ($n = 26$ [76%]) and caries formation in the affected teeth (24 [48%]).

Ectopic eruption of first permanent molars can lead to complications if left untreated. In the studies provided by Andrei et al., the main participant were patients aged between 5 and 9 years, and patients who needed a radiological examination for the diagnosis and treatment of dental or dento-maxillary diseases. The following exclusion criteria were applied: unclear or poor-quality radiographs; radiographs that belonged to patients who benefited from an orthodontic treatment before the panoramic radiograph was taken; patients who were undergoing orthodontic treatment when the radiograph was taken; and patients with local or general diseases that could influence dento-facial growth and development. Three degrees of severity were selected (moderate, severe, and very severe). The sample consisted of 438 patients, and 61 patients were diagnosed with ectopic eruption of first permanent molars (13.92%). Out of the 1752 analyzed molars, 103 were affected (5.87%). Patients with a moderate degree of ectopy were more frequently boys (56%, $n = 14$), while patients with a severe degree of ectopy were more frequently girls (52.8%, $n = 19$). Patients with a moderate degree of ectopy had significantly more frequently a unilateral position (57.1%, $n = 16$), while patients with a very severe degree of ectopy had significantly more frequently a bilateral position (36.4%, $n = 12$). The ectopic eruption was diagnosed at the level of the upper-right first permanent molar in a percentage of 18.4% ($n = 19$), at the level of the upper-left first permanent molar in a percentage of 17.5% ($n = 18$), at the level of the lower-right first permanent molar in a percentage of 32% ($n = 33$), and at the level of the lower-left first permanent molar in a percentage of 32% ($n = 33$). Although not very frequent, the ectopic eruption of first permanent molars is an important anomaly that should be early diagnosed, monitored and treated.

OPGs of 1104 patients with mean age 35.32 ± 16.63 were included. The total prevalence of developmental anomalies in this study was 36.3%

(401/1104). Male and female subjects with anomalies were 133 (33.2%) and 268 (66.8%) respectively. The prevalence of dilacerated teeth 300 (30.2%), congenitally missing teeth was 246 (24.7%), supernumerary teeth 18 (1.8%), talon cusp and taurodontism were seen in one patient each 1 (0.1%). Of these, a total of 15 (1.5%) anomalies were noted in pediatric patients.

Discussion

The main review objectives were to assess the international knowledge about the prevalence of eruptive anomalies in general population, mainly focusing on the group most recently affected by said affliction (the group of patients aged 8-18).

This review highlights that eruptive anomalies can be more common than medical knowledge and sources specify and how the difficulty of treatment can increase the longer said condition isn't solved by a dental medical professional. Previous studies have brought forth impressive statistics and even more impressive results in treating their participants.

The main dilemma is the lack of proper national statistics, Romania severely lacking in studies covering both the prevalence of certain pediatric dental problems and their treatment.

Conclusions

A better protocol must be elaborated in order to keep track of every pedodontic patient, the multitude of studies assessed showed increased difficulty in treating certain eruptive anomalies. Instating certain education programs for parents and future parents in order to communicate this international health concern is the way to improve the overall health of future generations.

Such an initiative needs a complex collaboration between dental health specialists, the Ministry of Education and The Ministry of Health. Educating the parents about the possible anomalies that their kids can suffer from can encourage them to establish frequent doctor's appointments and to frequently check the pre-eruptive state of their kids' dentition.

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